

ELIXIR Commissioned Service Training Platform, Work Package 2 - Consolidating the Training Platform Infrastructure

Establish a process of recognition for contribution to lesson templates (link to Data platform)

Tier: Technology

Priority Area: Federated Service Delivery

Executive Summary

The ELIXIR Training Platform's overarching objective is to establish a collaborative, visible, and standardised network of training resources. This milestone addresses the lack of consistent recognition for training material contributions, essential for community engagement and resource sustainability.

The primary objective was to establish a clear and sustainable process for recognising contributions to ELIXIR training lesson templates, specifically by exploring integration with [APICURON](#) for automated attribution in collaboration with the data platform.

During this period, we actively explored recognition frameworks through discussions with the APICURON team, Data Platform Credit and Recognition WP, and Training Platform WP2 members. During the BioHackathon2024 we engaged in [project 25](#) around research software credit practices and explored how lesson template contributions fit into this framework. This work established an ELIXIR Training Materials resource at APICURON, though direct lesson template integration is not yet complete. We conclude that defining a comprehensive training profile for the crediting framework is complex and requires broad community agreement.

An alternative recognition method identified involves making use of Zenodo and ORCID to create DOIs for training lessons and to credit authors and contributors. We have updated the lesson template with template files for providing Zenodo metadata and the template documentation with instructions on credit and recognition using Zenodo and ORCID.

We recommend continued collaboration with the Data Platform around a framework for recognition, including identifying tasks in the upcoming work program for defining a comprehensive crediting profile for Training Platform Contributions. This should include, but not be limited to, training materials contributions.

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Supporting Documents

Resources updated as a direct outcome of this milestone:

- [ELIXIR lesson template instructions](#)
- [ELIXIR-TrP-LessonTemplate-MkDocs](#)

Meeting notes and reports from connected tasks:

- [📄 APICURON and lesson template TC](#)
- [Biohackathon 2024 Project 25](#)
- [📄 Architecture: framework for recognition of Trainers and RSEs](#)

Dissemination Plans

The lesson template is currently published on GitHub and Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/records/7913092>, and on SPLASH

(<https://elixir-europe-training.github.io/ELIXIR-Training-SPLASH/elixir-lesson-template>) and

the ELIXIR lesson template instructions will be archived on Zenodo in the near future.

Additional dissemination will follow the completion of several related milestones and deliverables M2.11 (Maintain, support and update the ELIXIR Lesson Template), D2.5 (Documentation outlining the governance and maintenance structure for the Training GitHub organisation) and D2.6 (Documentation outlining the standard operating procedures for the Training Lesson Template Maintainers).